

Analysis of Influence of Card-Based Payment and Electronic Money on Money Supply

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ABSTRACT

The development of technology has changed many areas of people's lives, one of which is in the transaction process. Non-cash payment instruments such as non-cash payment instruments and electronic money are increasingly being used by the community. This increase affects the money supply. Through multiple linear regression tests, this study aims to see the influence of card-based payments and electronic money on the money supply. The data taken is the nominal credit card, debit card, electronic money as the independent variable, and the money supply as the dependent variable. The data taken is only limited to the period from January 2016 to April 2020. The results of the analysis show that debit cards and electronic money have a significant positive effect on the money supply, while credit cards have a significant negative effect on the money supply.

1. INTRODUCTION

Transactions are activities that cause changes in the owner's assets or finances, either decreasing or increasing (Roziq, Sofianti, et al. 2019). This transaction occurs because humans need items that are not owned (Kustono, Mas'ud, and Magvira 2019). Barter is a type of ancient transaction in which humans exchange goods for other goods. Increasingly, this type of transaction is considered inefficient due to the difficulty of assessing goods that are suitable for exchange for other goods (Kusuma, Putra, and Sudarno 2021). Because of these shortcomings, another medium of exchange that was easier to carry and more efficient emerged (Putri et al. n.d.). Starting from gold to metal, it was used by humans as a means of payment. Until now, what is still widely used is in the form of paper cash and coins (Prasetyo 2019). Money is a very important tool in everyday life. Money as a means of payment cannot be separated from its role as a tool for economic transactions around the world (Luthfiyatul Farida,

Roziq, and Maria Wardayati 2019). Money can be used as an indicator of a country's economy because all economic activity will involve money in it (Hidayatullah, Budi Sulistiyo, and Hisamuddin Jurusan Akuntansi 2019). Therefore, money is used by the central bank as an indicator for implementing policies in the economic sector, particularly in banking and finance (Afifi, Kustono, and Nuha 2022).

Technology, information, and communication that are become more modern have greatly contributed to the changes in more efficient transactions (Maulidah and Winarno 2022). The development of technology, information, and communication changes the condition of the payment system, one of which is transactions (List, Arif, and Santosa Putra 2022). The transaction is no longer uses paper money and coins only but also uses other financial instruments, namely non-cash (As sajad, Puspita, and Sudarno 2021).

The National Non-Cash Movement (*Gerakan Nasional Non Tunai*) was launched in

2014 which aims to increase public awareness of the use of non-cash payment instruments (Adita, Irmadariyani, and Shulthoni 2021). If the community has used non-cash instruments in their transactions, a Less Cash Society will be formed (Santosa Putra et al. 2020). Non-cash payment instruments include card-based payment instruments (*Alat Pembayaran Menggunakan Kartu/ APMK*) and electronic money. In today's digital era, Cashless Payment refers to an economic arrangement in which goods and services are transacted without cash (Akhalmeh and Ohiokha 2012).

Figure 1. Non-cash transaction volume for 2013-2019

The use of electronic money in Indonesia has increased in 2017-2019 and it is possible to continue onwards. This increase was due to technological developments and the ease of use of electronic money.

Bank Indonesia as the monetary authority is the institution authorized to maintain the stability of the payment system (Sulistiyo, al Ardi, and Roziq 2020). Financial system stability can be seen through several indicators, for example, the interest rate and the money supply which the development must always be controlled. The aim is so as not to have a bad impact on national financial stability (Kustono and Nanggala 2020). The increase in non-cash transactions is expected to cause transparency in the circulation of money and slowing down the money supply in country.

(Ramadani 2016) defines e-money as a payment instrument that can be used for various types of payments (multi-purposed). Generally acceptable is the condition that an item can be used as a means of payment (Pratama, Purnamawati, and Sayekti 2019). Electronic money is an example of a payment instrument

that is generally accepted today (Kustono 2020). Bank Indonesia as the authorized party in the payment system has updated the regulations governing electronic payment instruments, namely *Peraturan Bank Indonesia Nomor 20/6 / PBI / 2018*.

Monetary authorities predict an increase in non-cash transactions will lead to transparency in the circulation of money and may slow down the money supply. Kaminsky, Lizondo, and Reinhart (Rusydia, Rani, and Hasib 2019) said that indicators, such as the balance of payments, interest rates, economic growth, inflation, exchange rates, and the money supply are the causes of the economic crisis hitting countries in the world (Roos Ana, Budi Sulistiyo, and Prasetyo 2021). Usually, this indicator is used as an early indicator of an impending crisis (Kurrohman 2020). In Indonesia, the task of maintaining economic stability and economic system stability and detecting the impending crisis is Bank Indonesia as the monetary authority (Suyitno, Miqdad, and Sayekti 2020). Financial system stability is a stable financial system that is able to allocate sources of funds and absorb shocks that occur so as to prevent disruptions to real sector activities and the financial system (Rusdianasari 2018). Indicators in assessing financial system stability are interest rates and the money supply, which the development of these indicators must always be controlled so as not to have a negative impact (Roziq, Abshor, et al. 2019).

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESE

Money Demand Theory

Immadudin Yuliadi in his book *Monetary Economics* explains that the money demand is determined by the size of the volume of economic transactions that are proportional to national income (Mashadi 2018). In Indonesia, there are two types of payment instruments, those are cash and non-cash payment. Based on research conducted by (Lintangsari et al. 2018) notes that debit cards and electronic money have a significant effect on the money supply. The conclusions of the research conducted by (Fitri et al. 2017) is that credit cards have a negative effect on the money supply while debit cards and electronic money have a positive effect on the money supply. That's why write proposed hypothesis.

Payment Instrument

Cash is physical money that is ready to be spent and is in the hands of society (Miqdad and Rizky Izzalqurny 2019). Cashless money can be used primarily for payments with small and not too large nominal (Solikin 2017). The cash can be in the form of paper or coins (Kusuma and Shulthoni 2021). Paper cash is the most popular when it comes to payment among Indonesians and the most popular compared to other forms of cash (Prasetyo et al. 2020). This is due to paper are easy to carry despite its value is greater than coins (Nuha, Miqdad, and Sulistiyo 2021).

Non-cash payment instruments are now popular because of their practicality when carried and when transactions happen (Roziq and Sukarno 2021). Non-cash payment instruments can be in the form of card-based payments and electronic money (Putri, Miqdad, and Sulistiyo 2020a). The card-based payment includes debit cards and credit cards. The difference between card-based payment and electronic money is regarding the status of consumers (Roziq, Marizca, and Kustono 2021). The card-based payment users must be registered as card-issuing bank customers in order to make transactions, while electronic money users don't need to be customers of the issuing bank (Nawangarsi et al. 2020). The regulations regarding card-based payment are contained in Bank Indonesia Regulation Number 11/11 / PBI / 2009 and Number 14/13 / PBI / 2012. The card-based payment facilitates transactions that occur in the community because it can cover cash shortages, namely goods carried only in the form of cards whose value can reach tens of millions.

If a debit card or credit card needs to authorize online, it is another matter for electronic money that can be authorized offline by electronic money users (Ely, Effendi, and Mas'ud 2019). Bank Indonesia Regulation Number 11/12 / PBI / 2009 is a regulation that governs Electronic Money which explains that electronic money is a separate part of APMK (Irmadariyani et al. 2019). Since it was legalized as a legal payment instrument, there have been many electronic money issuers in Indonesia as of June 2020, reaching 37 companies.

Money Supply

The money supply is the obligation of the monetary system to the domestic private sector (Mashadi 2018). Money Supply can be calculated by adding up the total currency and demand

deposits circulating in the community (Purnamawati et al. 2019a). The regulations regarding the money supply in Indonesia are contained in Bank Indonesia Regulation Number 17/8 / PBI / 2015 concerning monetary regulation and supervision. Money supply can be divided into money in the narrow sense (M1) and money in the broad sense (M2). M1 consists of total demand deposits and total currency, while M2 consists of M1 plus holdings.

Hypothesis

The hypothesis is a temporary answer to the questions asked during research (Roziq et al. 2020). Hypotheses can be explained from many different points of view according to the field of research. Based on the results of previous studies that have been described, the hypothesis proposed is as follows:

1. H0: card-based payment and electronic money have no effect on the money supply
2. H1: Credit cards have a positive effect on the money supply
3. H2: Debit cards have a positive effect on the money supply
4. H3: Electronic money has a positive effect on the money supply

3. RESEARCH METHOD

Research Design

This research is a type of quantitative research by testing the nominal credit card, debit card, electronic money as an independent variable with the money supply as the dependent variable using statistics.

Types and Sources of Data

This type of data uses quantitative data because the data is in the form of numbers (Purniawan, Mas'ud, and Wulandari 2019). The type of data taken is data that is chronologically arranged according to a monthly basis from January 2016 to April 2020, so that it includes the type of monthly data.

This data source is obtained from official collecting institutions such as BPS and Bank Indonesia so that it can be categorized as secondary data.

Population and Sample

The population, the nominal amount of card-based payment transactions includes credit

cards, debit cards, electronic money, and money supply.

The sample taken from this research is the nominal amount of card-based payment transactions including debit cards, credit cards, electronic money, and money supply from January 2016 to April 2020.

Data Analysis Method

The study used multiple regression analysis to determine the relationship between variables. Multiple linear regression is a continuation of simple linear where the independent variable is more than one and the dependent variable is one (Kuncorowati, Miqdad, and Roziq 2021). Prior to the regression test, the classical assumption test was carried out. The purpose of the classical assumption test is to determine whether or not there is residual normality, autocorrelation, multicollinearity, and heteroscedasticity and to see the feasibility of the data before analysis (Putri, Miqdad, and Sulistiyo 2020b).

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Result

Normality test

One method to test data normality is to use the Kolmogorov-Smirnov one-sample test to see whether the data is normally distributed or not. A significance value that exceeds 0.05 indicates that the data has been normally distributed.

Table 1. Normality Test Result

	Unstandardized residual
N	52
Asymp. Sig (2-tailed)	.200 ^{c,d}

It can be seen in table 1 that the significance value is 0.200. This value has exceeded 0.05, which means the data has been normally distributed.

Heteroscedasticity test

Heteroscedasticity test was used to see the residual variants in the data. The method taken is to see by looking at the pattern on the scatterplot.

Figure 2. Scatter Plot Result

It can be seen in figure 2 that a certain pattern is not formed and the points are scattered over the entire area (Agus Winarno et al. 2021). So it can be said that there is no indication of heteroscedasticity so that the data feasible to be tested at the next stage (Purnamawati et al. 2019b).

Multicollinearity Test

The method used is to see the VIF value and Tolerance is used to see whether there is a linearity relationship between variables

Table 2. Multicollinearity Test Result

Model	Collinearity Statistics		
	Tolerance	VIF	
1	(Constant)		
	Kartu Kredit	.285	3.505
	Kartu Debit	.205	4.870
	Uang Elektronik	.546	1.832

It can be seen in the table below that the tolerance value of the tested variables is >0.1 and the VIF is <10, so it can be concluded that multicollinearity does not occur between the variables.

Multiple Linear Regression Test

Multiple regression analysis tests to determine the relationship between variables. Through the coefficient of determination denoted by R square, it can be seen whether the data is feasible or not.

Table 3. The coefficient of determination

Model	R	R Square
1	.933 ^a	.870

The coefficient of determination shows the number 0.870 which means the value is close to 1 so that the regression model can be said to be feasible for use.

Table 4. Partial T-Test

Model	t	Sig.
(Constant)	9.836	.000
Kartu Kredit	-3.928	.000
Kartu Debit	7.261	.000
Uang Elektronik	6.572	.000

T-test is used to test partially between the independent variables and the dependent variable individually. The significance value for both credit cards, debit cards, and electronic money shows the number 0.00 so it can be said that the hypothesis H1, H2, and H3 are accepted.

Discussion

Analysis of the Effect of Credit Card Nominal on money supply

M1 in a narrow sense is the total currency, demand deposits, and savings circulating in society. The effect of technological sophistication has resulted in currency being replaced by non-cash, including card-based payment and electronic money. The increasing use of card-based payment and electronic money reduces the demand for currency and demand deposits.

The analysis carried out is to see whether or not a credit card has an effect on M1 in a narrow sense. Based on the results of processing using SPSS 26, it can be seen in Table 3 that the coefficient of determination is 0.870, so it means that 87% of the variation in money supply can be explained by independent variables, which are credit cards, debit cards, and electronic money. The remaining 13% is explained by factors other than variables in the analysis model being carried out.

In the partial t-test, it can be seen in Table 5 that the significance value of the Credit Card is 0.00 so that the value is <0.05 . In Table 4 it can also be seen that the t-count value for credit cards is -3.928. After calculating the t-table value of the credit card is 2.012063. Because $t\text{-table} > t\text{-count}$,

it can be concluded that the hypothesis H0 is rejected, while H1 is accepted.

The analysis carried out resulted in the conclusion that credit cards have a negative and significant effect on money supply. This is consistent with research conducted by (Fitri et al. 2017) which resulted in credit card analysis having a significant and negative effect on money supply. This means that an increase in credit cards will be followed by a decrease in the money supply. Conversely, a decrease in credit card usage will be followed by an increase in money supply.

Analysis of the Effect of Debit Card Transactions on Money Supply

In table 4.5 it can be seen that the debit card significance value is less than 0.05 with a value of 0.00, while the t-table is $7,261 > t\text{-count}$, which has a value of 2.012063. This means that H0 is rejected, while H2 is accepted, which means that the debit card has a positive effect on the money supply. The indication of this result is that an increase in debit cards will be followed by an increase in the money value because debit card transactions are included in the demand deposit category that affects M1.

This conclusion is in accordance with the research conducted by (Devi Kartika Sari 2020) which states that debit card transactions have a significant and positive effect on the money value. The use of debit cards has become commonplace in the community. In fact, many companies transfer workers' salaries via debit ATMs.

In accordance with the working paper conducted by Parmono (Lintangsari et al. 2018), the conclusion is that the development of card-based payment causes the erosion of the savings function to become savings that can be withdrawn at any time. Savings using a debit card are classified as part of demand deposits in money supply in a narrow sense (M1). It is no longer part of the money supply in a broad sense (M2).

Analysis of the Effect of Electronic Money on Money Supply

In table 4, it can be seen that the significance value of Electronic Money is less than 0.05 with a value of 0.00 and the t-count is

2.012063 <t-table with a value of 6,572. The conclusion that can be drawn is that H0 is rejected, while H2 is accepted, which means that electronic money has a positive effect on money supply. An indication of the outcome is that an increase in electronic money will be followed by an increase in money supply.

This research is in line with the research conducted by (Fauzie and S Istanto 2014) which concluded that electronic money has a significant and positive effect on money supply. In electronic money, there is the term float, which means that an amount of funds belonging to an issuer is in electronic money, whether it has been used, it has not been billed by the merchant. These funds are categorized as liquid funds and are classified as cash or demand deposits which affect the money supply.

5. CONCLUSION, IMPLICATION, SUGGESTION, AND LIMITATIONS

From the results of the credit card t-test it can be concluded that H0 is rejected while H1 is accepted. This means that there is a significant negative effect between payment transactions using credit cards on the money supply.

From the results of the debit card t-test it can be concluded that H0 is rejected while H2 is accepted. This means that there is a significant positive effect between payment transactions using a debit card on the money supply.

From the results of the t-test for electronic money, it can be concluded that H0 is rejected while H3 is accepted. This means that there is a significant positive effect between payment transactions using electronic money on the money supply.

It is recommended that further research be able to develop research results by adding or changing the variables studied due to the limitations of this study only using a period of less than 5 years. In addition, the faster technological advances can increase knowledge and change the social order that occurs in society can make this research less relevant in the future.

It is better that an authorized institution in promoting non-cash payments so that people can adapt to technological advances. Modernization in society will make benefits in today's rapidly developing era.

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